

A Zeagrani for 2026 🌽🍸

*On writing as thinking, cocktails as cultural mashups, and why pauses matter.
A brief New Year note before the blog goes quiet—and a glass is raised.*

I started this blog [a little over four years ago](#), mostly as a place to think out loud. I didn't expect much. What I didn't expect at all was the feedback—thoughtful messages, kind words, disagreements that actually made me think, and a steady stream of positive vibes from readers around the world. That part still surprises me.

As always, this blog has been many things at once: commentary, opinion, occasional provocation—and yes, sometimes therapy. Writing has been one of my ways to process ideas, frustrations, and a fair amount of anxiety. It still works.

As we enter 2026, I'm going to pause the blog for a few weeks. Not because I'm out of things to say—quite the opposite. I have a long list of ideas and half-finished drafts. There's simply too much happening right now: projects multiplying, GPUs spinning, brain at capacity. You know the feeling. Check [here](#) and [here](#).

But before hitting pause, let's celebrate.

[Over the past couple of weeks in Mexico](#), I came across an unusual spirit made from a maize landrace—a whiskey de maiz that immediately spoke to me. I don't like gin (sorry—for reasons still unclear, it reliably messes me up; call it gluten, botanicals, or bad karma). This maize spirit, however, turned out to be a perfect stand-in for a Negroni (ciao, Italia).

Thus was born the **Zeagrani** (*Zea mays* + Negroni, for the non-botanists and non-drinkers).

How to make a Zeagrani:

30 ml whiskey de maiz

25 ml Campari

20 ml sweet vermouth (go lighter than usual to not overtake the corn spirit)

Big ice, long stir, orange peel

[And it shall forever be known as the #Zeagrani](#)

It's a drink that shouldn't work, but does. Much like many good ideas.

The bottle itself carries a line that perfectly captures why this drink feels right:

“Rendimos tributo a los campesinos que han preservado los cultivos de especies nativas y antiguas.” | We pay tribute to the farmers who have preserved native and ancient crops.

[An Aztec maize farmer—as depicted in the Florentine Codex.](#)

Science, culture, agriculture, inheritance—all in a glass.

So here's to 2026.

Here's to pauses that are intentional.

And here's to unexpected combinations that turn out better than planned.

Cheers. Happy New Year. ¡Feliz Año Nuevo! 🍷

— Sophien

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